

WINDING PATTERN AND NUMBER OF LAYERS EFFECTS ON FILAMENT-WOUND CYLINDERS UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSION

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Introduction

- Filament Winding:
 - High fiber content and low void content;
 - Repeatability;
 - Precision in placing fibers;

ASME, 2012

Composites World, 2022

Bodea, 2021

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 - High fiber content and low void content;
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- Material and geometrical properties;

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{E_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix}$$

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$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{c^4}{E_1} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_1} \right) s^2 c^2 + \frac{s^4}{E_2}$$

Peters, 2011

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- Winding pattern WP ;
- Number of layers N :

- Past researches regarding *WP* influence:

Author (s)	Load case	Approach	Number of layers (+ α / $-\alpha$)	Pattern range	Stiffness	Stress / Strength	(%)
Claus (1992)	Buckling (axial compression)	Experimental	-	-	Yes	Yes	-
Hahn et al. (1994)	Buckling (axial compression)	Experimental	1	1-26	No	Yes	-
Rousseau et al. (1999)	Axial tension	Experimental	6	2-11	No	Yes	-
	Internal pressure			2-11	-	No	-
Morozov (2006)	Internal pressure	Numerical	1	2-8	-	Yes	33.40
Moreno et al. (2008)	Buckling (external pressure)	Experimental	7	1-5	-	No	-
Mian et al. (2011)	Internal pressure	Numerical	1	2-8	-	Yes	34.87
Wen et al. (2013)	Axial tension	Experimental	7	1-5	-	Yes	
Azevedo et al. (2019)	Buckling (axial compression)	Experimental	1	1-5	Yes	Yes	
Guo et al. (2020)	Buckling (axial compression)	Numerical	7	4-10	-	Yes	4.21
	Buckling (external pressure)	Numerical	7	4-10	-	Yes	1.15
Lisbôa et al. (2020)	Radial compression	Experimental	1	1-10	No	Yes	
Stabla et al. (2021)	Radial compression	Numerical	1	2-7	Yes	Yes	
Stabla et al. (2022)	Radial compression	Experimental	1	1-3	Yes	-	
Lisboa et al. (2022)	Radial compression	Numerical	1	1-3	-	Yes	

Objective

- To numerically investigate the influence of winding pattern as function of the number of layers and winding angle on the mechanical behavior of FW tubes.

Methodology

- Definition of geometrical properties:
 - Tow height: 0.25 mm;
 - Cylinder length: 250 mm;
 - Mandrel's diameter: 136 mm;
- Material properties:
 - $E_1 = 139900$ MPa;
 - $E_2 = E_3 = 8520$ MPa;
 - $G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 4260$ MPa;
 - $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.26$.

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- Constructive parameters:
 - α ($^\circ$): 15, 25, 35, 45, 55, and 65;

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 - α (°): 15, 25, 35, 45, 55, and 65;
 - WPs: 0, 1, 3, 5, and 7;
 - N : 1, 2, 4, and 6;
 - $6 \times 5 \times 4 = 120$ models.

$N = 1$

$N = 2$

$N = 4$

$N = 6$

Methodology

- Shell elements (SHELL281):
 - 8 nodes (Serendipity);
 - 6 DOF's;
 - 9 integration points;
 - Triangular shape;
 - Mindlin-Reissner theory (moderate thickness);

Ansys, 2021

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- Boolean operations;
- Cylindrical (r, θ, z) and local $(1, 2, 3)$ coordinate systems.

Methodology

- Boundary conditions:
 - Right edge clamped;
 - Left edge with free translation;
 - Both edges with free expansion/contraction (u_r);
- Load condition:
 - Axial compression load at reference node;
 - Target stress: 500 MPa.

Methodology

- Stress measurements:
 - Local coordinates;
 - Evaluated along circumferential direction, every 3°;
 - 1st location: Center line (CL) – Along the circumferential crossover (zig-zag lines), at the coordinate $z = 0$ mm;
 - 2nd location: Shifted Center Line (SCL) – 5 mm offset from CL;
 - 3rd location: Mid-triangle line (MTL) – At the midpoint between two CL's (1/4 of diamond's width);
- Stiffness measurement:
 - Directly from displacement considering the deviation relative to the reference configuration (WP = 0);

$$K_{ij} = \frac{\partial F_i}{\partial u_j}$$

Results

- Stress concentrations ($N = 1$, $WP = 7$, $\alpha = 35^\circ$):

Results

- σ_1 as function of WP ($N = 1$, $\alpha = 35^\circ$, bottom layer):

Results

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Results

- σ_2 and τ_{12} as function of WP ($N = 1$, $\alpha = 35^\circ$, bottom layer):

— MTL — SCL — CL

Results

- σ_1 as function of N ($WP = 5$, $\alpha = 35^\circ$, bottom layer):

Results

- Stiffness:

Results

- Stiffness deviation from the reference configuration ($WP = 0$):

Results

- σ_1 as function of α ($N = 1$, $WP = 7$, bottom layer, MTL):

— 15° — 25° — 35° — 45° — 55° — 65°

Conclusions

- Stress concentrations observed in the interweaving regions;
- Away from these regions, stress values of regular laminates are observed;
- Stress concentrations of one layer propagate to all the others;
- Their magnitudes are considerably reduced by adding more layers;
- Axial stiffness is sensitive to the size of the HCO region;
- *WP*'s influence on axial stiffness is negligible for more than 2 layers.

Thank you!
